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Reducing indwelling urinary catheter use in elderly care: Determinants, strategies, and contextual approaches for improved patient care in Austria and Switzerland

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Background:

While indwelling urinary catheters (IUCs) provide essential clinical benefits when used under appropriate indications, the frequent inappropriate placement—occurring in approximately 50% of cases—poses significant risks to patient safety, especially among older persons. Safety risks are catheter-associated infections, injuries and reduction of patients' quality of life. To improve patient safety and quality of care, it is crucial to further develop and refine initiatives aimed at reducing the use of non-indicated IUCs.

Aim:

Our aim is to identify the factors influencing IUC use as perceived and experienced by healthcare providers, managers, patients, long-term care residents, and their family members. Additionally, we aim to detect fitting de-implementation strategies to minimise the duration of IUC use.

Method:

We performed a qualitative evidence synthesis to explore the factors contributing to the inadequate use of IUCs in elderly patients and the strategies employed to reduce its use. A systematic search was conducted in MEDLINE, Scopus, and CINAHL for studies published from January 1, 2000 to March 11, 2024. Following the Cochrane-Campbell Handbook for Qualitative Evidence Synthesis, we utilized a thematic synthesis approach. Building on these findings, we conducted interviews and focus groups with healthcare personnel, managers as well as patients and residents in five hospitals and three to four long-term care facilities in Austria and Switzerland.

Results:

The factors contributing to IUC overuse as identified in the qualitative evidence included differing perceptions of benefits and risks, low prioritization of the issue, limited access to or perceived suitability of alternatives, high nurse workload and staff shortages and non-adherence to guidelines (moderate confidence in findings). Additionally, deviations from protocol responsibilities, ineffective nurse-physician communication, documentation challenges, and inadequate training were associated with IUC use (low confidence in findings). Identified strategies for reducing IUC use included training for nurses and physicians on IUC placement, supporting clinicians via reminders to remove catheters or review the adequacy of IUC use, improving electronic documentation systems and revising guidelines to empowering nurses. Infrastructure strategies involved increased staffing and increasing use of alternatives. The results of the interviews will be used to contextualize and enrich the findings from the qualitative evidence synthesis, providing a deeper understanding of the themes and perspectives identified. The empirical study results will be available in November 2025.

Implications for research and healthcare practice:

Future research should actively engage patients and families to better understand the determinants of IUC use. Evaluating alternative urine collection methods is essential, as their perceived unmanageability hinders adoption.

Additionally, testing a research approach to reduce data collection efforts by incorporating information from existing literature as a stimulus in focus groups and interviews should be considered.